

HYBRID TREES

Many Natural Hybrids, as Well as Sports, to Be Found—Artificial Hybridization Leads to Production of Trees Valuable for Their Great Vigor—
What Has Been Done and What May Be Done

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BREEDING short-lived plants and orchard trees is now a well-established art, but breeding timber trees has hardly been undertaken. The importance of such work is being recognized, however, and Prof. Augustine Henry has made a notable contribution in his study of natural and artificial hybrids.¹ His recent paper on the black poplars² offers some excellent examples of the occurrence of natural hybrids and the value of artificial ones.

The cultivated species of *Populus* which have been found desirable for commercial plantings, he points out, are without exception of "unnatural" origin, in that they are either sports or hybrids, and not ordinary species.

"A sport is usually a solitary phenomenon, arising either as a sporadic peculiar seedling from a seed, or developing out of a bud on a tree as a single branch with some peculiarity of twig or leaf. A sport may be looked upon as a freak, not forming the starting-point of a new species, but speedily becoming extinct if left to nature. Sports, when of interest on account of the curiosity or the beauty of their appearance, are propagated usually by grafts, cuttings, or layers; being only in rare cases perpetuated by seed. Some sports are due to arrested development. The tree, in the course of its life, often passes through stages, like those of an insect. The seedling of many species differs from the adult tree as a larva from a butterfly. The infant ash has simple

leaves. The sport known as the simple-leaf ash is simply a seedling ash, which has never progressed to maturity and may be called a persistent larval form. The Irish yew was found in 1767 as a seedling on the mountain behind Florence Court in Fermanagh, and is characterised by all the branches being directed vertically upwards and all the leaves spreading radially around the twig. This is apparently also the seedling stage preserved. All the myriads of Irish yews, now scattered throughout the world, are cuttings either from the original tree at Florence Court or from trees that were derived from those cuttings.

THE LOMBARDY POPLAR

"This upright, so-called fastigate form may occur as a sport in any species, the best known being the Lombardy poplar, which originated on the banks of the Po about 1700 and subsequently spread over the world. The Lombardy poplar and Irish yew are striking examples of the immense number of individual trees of a sport that may exist, this abundance being entirely due to human agency. Left to nature, these two remarkable forms would never have multiplied, and would have ceased to exist, once the original trees had succumbed to old age or injury. The fastigate sport is of rare occurrence in most genera, usually only a single original tree being recorded. Amongst, however, the cypress and juniper families, fastigate seedlings are

¹ Henry, Augustine, "The Artificial Production of Vigorous Trees," *Jour. of Dept. of Agric. and Tech. Instr. for Ireland*, XV, 1, 1915. Reviewed by W. H. Lamb in *Proc. Soc. Am. Foresters*, X, 2, April, 1915.

² Henry, Augustine, "The Black Poplars." *Trans. Royal Scot. Arboricult. Soc.*, pp. 14-27, January, 1916; also in *Gard. Chron.* (London), LVI, pp. 1, 46, 66, July, 1914.

A NATURAL HICKORY HYBRID

This tree, which is believed to be a cross between the pecan (*Hicoria pecan*) and the shellbark hickory (*H. laciniosa*) is standing in a rich river bottom 12 miles from Mt. Vernon, Ind. Like most first-generation hybrids, it is a vigorous and rapid grower, but perhaps for this very reason its leaves and branches are tender and succulent—at any rate it seems to attract all the insect pests in the neighborhood. This is not always the case with hybrid trees, however, for many of them are superior to their parents. The immense size of the nuts which this hybrid bears can be judged from one which the man at the right of the picture holds in his hand; in Fig. 15 a single one of them is shown natural size. Photograph from the United States Department of Agriculture. (Fig. 12.)

common; and the upright habit appears to come true from seed. The Mediterranean cypress has been known in this peculiar narrow form for centuries, but always cultivated. In the wild state, as in the mountains of Cyprus, the tree is widespreading in habit. The common juniper, however, is often fastigate in the wild forests of Scandinavia. This exemplifies the difficulty of strict definition in nature, as the fastigate habit, which is a rare sport in most trees, becomes in the junipers and cypresses almost a normal form, capable of being perpetuated by seed."

If sports among forest trees are more common than has been generally supposed, the same is true of hybrids. Prof. Henry mentions the hollies of Great Britain, which include numerous hybrids and sports, as well as good species. American naturalists are familiar with the hawthorns, whose hybridity has lately been demonstrated by Prof. E. C. Jeffrey of Harvard and his pupils.³ The extraordinary state of affairs in the hawthorn genus (*Crataegus*) may best be realized if we recall that more than 700 alleged species of *Crataegus* have been described, whereas, of all other trees in the United States put together, there are only some 600 species.

HYBRID OAKS

The willows are known to hybridize widely, and the various species of oaks readily cross with any of their near relatives that happen to be growing near. Prof. Henry cites an interesting oak hybrid in England:

"The results of the experimental sowings of the seeds of numerous elms which I made in 1909, together with an investigation into the history of the Lucombe oak, given in a paper read by me at the Linnean Society on the seventh of April, 1910, threw new light on many hybrid trees in cultivation, which had not previously been recognized as such, in spite of the fact that no one could find these trees anywhere in the wild state. The statement often made that a particular tree was a 'variety of garden origin' was no

explanation. The Lucombe oak was observed in the Exeter Nursery in 1765 as a seedling, which differed from its parent, a Turkey oak (*Quercus cerris*), in being much more fast in growth and in retaining its leaves during winter till March. Lucombe propagated this seedling by grafting, and believed it to be simply a sport of the Turkey oak. In 1792 it bore acorns from which numerous seedlings were raised, no two of which were alike, while some strongly resembled in bark and leaves the Cork oak (*Q. suber*). Lucombe's son then correctly surmised that it was a hybrid—the flower on the Turkey oak, from which the acorn producing it was formed, having been fertilized by the pollen of an adjoining large Cork oak.

"This case illustrates several well-known laws in regard to hybrids:

"1. The first cross is usually of exceptional vigor, more vigorous than either parent.

"2. When the first-cross reproduces itself by seed, the second generation consists of classes of individuals, which differ from one another and from their parent. The first-cross never comes true from seed, but produces a mixed and varied offspring.

"3. None of the individuals of the second generation equal in vigor the first-cross. This was also clearly established in the case of the Lucombe oak.

"Other common trees, of which no history is recorded, doubtless originated in the same way as the Lucombe oak, namely, as chance seedlings (the result of accidental crossing by wind or an insect), which observant nurserymen or gardeners found desirable to propagate on account of their vigor. The introduction in quantity into Europe during the seventeenth century of North American trees, which grew alongside similar but distinct European species in parks and gardens, was the occasion of considerable hybridization. Trees like the black Italian poplar and the London plane, which have nowhere been seen wild, are intermediate in botanical characters between an American and a

³Standish, L. M. What is Happening to the Hawthorns? JOURNAL OF HEREDITY, VII, 6, pp. 266-279, June, 1916.

European species in each case, and are undoubtedly first-crosses. These two trees have been traced back to 1700, about which date the American parents had been long enough in Europe to bear flowers."

THE POPLAR HYBRIDS

The black poplars, it will be remembered, are represented by only two species, one native to Europe and the other to North America, and both having well-marked geographical varieties. The European species, *Populus nigra*, is distinguished from the American tree, *Populus deltoidea*, by the absence of cilia (tiny projecting hairs) on the margins of the leaves, and by the absence of glands on the base of the leaf-blades in front. These characteristics are present on the leaves of the American black poplar. The author designates the glabrous form of the European black poplar as *Populus nigra* var. *typica*, and the pubescent form as *Populus nigra* var. *betulifolia*. The glabrous black poplars of North America are given as *Populus deltoidea* var. *monolifera*, growing from Ontario to Pennsylvania, and *Populus deltoidea* var. *occidentalis*, growing in the region directly east of the Rocky Mountains, from Saskatchewan and Alberta to New Mexico and western Texas. The pubescent American black poplar is *Populus deltoidea* var. *missouriensis*, which grows in the south and southeastern parts of the United States, ascending the Mississippi basin to Missouri. This variety, the author believes, may be taken as the type of *Populus deltoidea*, being most likely to be the form represented by the original description of Marshall.

THE CAROLINA POPLAR

But the chief importance of Prof. Henry's contribution lies in his extensive study of the cultivated black poplars, which has resulted in the valuable discovery that they are almost invariably of hybrid origin. Most interesting to American foresters is the discovery made concerning the Carolina poplar which has been so extensively cultivated here. A great many of our writers

have felt that this name, "Carolina poplar," was one invented by nurserymen to overcome the unpopularity of the cottonwood. Some have even believed that the *Populus nigra* of the trade was nothing but our *Populus deltoidea* grown in France and Belgium and returned to America under the false designation. Much relief, therefore, will be experienced by reputable dealers, and by their patrons as well, at having Prof. Henry's determination of the true nature of the cultivated black poplars, and especially the Carolina poplar. Originally the author felt that this tree was merely a form of our *Populus deltoidea*, which had undergone mutation in its floral parts after cultivation in Europe. But now it is determined that the tree is a hybrid between the true black poplar of Europe (*Populus nigra*) and the southern form of our native black poplar (*Populus deltoidea* var. *missouriensis*).

In addition to the Carolina poplar, a number of hybrids are illustrated and described by Prof. Henry which have been derived from the typical black poplar of Europe and the northern form of our black poplar (*Populus deltoidea* var. *monolifera*). These are: *P. serotina* Hartig, *P. regenerata* Schneider, *P. Eugenei* Simon-Louis, *P. marilandica* Bosc., and *P. Henryana* Dode. Further, two forms are described as having arisen from the hybridization of the European black poplar with hybrid forms. These are *P. robusta* Schneider and *P. Lloydii* Henry.

WHY NOT A HYBRID SYCAMORE?

Viewing this work in the light of the previous researches of Prof. Henry on the artificial production of vigorous trees, it will be observed that the author has first demonstrated the practical importance of propagating first generation hybrids. He has then ascertained that the poplars already recognized as especially desirable for cultivation are of hybrid origin. The two papers, therefore, present most forcibly the great importance of initiating intensive work on the artificial production of vigorous trees, and suggest that special attention be directed toward the hybrid-

A CLUSTER OF PECAN NUTS

The pecan is a species of hickory and its nuts, here shown natural size, are enclosed in pods or husks. It is becoming an important crop in the southern states, due to the isolation and propagation of superior varieties instead of dependence on mixed seedlings, as in the past. Photograph from the United States Department of Agriculture. (Fig. 13.)

ization of species of many genera. Our sycamore, *Platanus occidentalis*, for example, is one of the most rapid growing of our hardwood trees. But it is afflicted with a fungus disease which causes the leaves to fall almost immediately after they have appeared in the spring. The restored foliage does not appear to suffer, however, and the tree

does not appear to be greatly retarded in its annual growth, for notwithstanding this infirmity, the tree holds first place in size among North American hardwoods.⁴ But the tree is being replaced by the European sycamore or plane (*Platanus orientalis*) in street and landscape plantings, as the exotic species appears to be immune to this disease.

⁴ Lamb, W. H., in JOURNAL OF HEREDITY, VI, 9, pp. 424-428, September, 1915.

The possibility of producing a vigorous hybrid between these trees is immediately suggested. In fact one may already exist. The London plane, *Platanus acerifolia*, has never been found growing wild and exhibits characteristics intermediate between the American and the European planes. But without doubt, it would be highly profitable to experiment with hybrids of known parentage.

A large field for profitable research is thus opened up by the possibility of artificially producing trees having exceptional vigor. The oaks, chestnuts, lindens, and many other important genera offer a fertile field for experimentation. And at the present time the importance of such work can scarcely be overestimated.

How little has been done is made strikingly clear by Prof. Henry's historical review. He ascribes to Klotzsch the credit for the first hybridization, with the production of pine, oak, alder and elm hybrids at Berlin in 1845. The results were good, but the work attracted little attention.

VIGOROUS WALNUT HYBRIDS

The frequent production of hybrid walnuts in California led Luther Burbank to take up this genus, and he called attention to the valuable qualities of the first-generation hybrids, which grow so rapidly that experienced foresters will scarcely credit the figures. Trees of the so-called Paradox walnut (*Juglans regia*, the Persian or "English" \times *J. californica*) at Santa Rosa measure 80 feet in height and 6 feet in girth after fifteen years of growth. The hybrid known as Royal (*J. californica* \times *J. nigra*, the black walnut of the eastern United States), appears to be an even more rapid grower, one specimen being credited with a height of 100 feet and a girth of 9 feet after only sixteen years of growth. Another magnificent walnut hybrid is that on the James River, Virginia, which was described by Peter Bisset recently.⁵

As to the quality of the wood of these hybrid trees—a point of prime impor-

tance to foresters—Prof. Henry remarks:

"It is a popular belief that fast-grown timber is necessarily soft and comparatively worthless. This is a fact in most conifers; but in one class of broad-leaf trees, the wood of which is characterized by large pores in the inner part of the annual ring, the contrary is true, as the faster the timber of these trees is grown the stronger and denser it becomes. This class includes oak, ash, chestnut, hickory, and walnut, the species in fact that *par excellence* produce the most valuable timber.

"All the more reason, then, for efforts to produce fast-growing crosses in the case of these precious trees. To quote from the conclusion of my paper of 1910: 'In countries like our own the only hope of salvation for forestry is in growing timber rapidly; and we have been helped in that by the introduction of fast-growing conifers like the larch, the Corsican pine, and the Douglas fir. But it is essential to grow the more valuable classes of non-coniferous timber.' The difficulty of growing the ordinary species of oak, ash, and walnut is the long period required for their maturity, which renders hopeless, except on the best soils, all chance of an adequate financial return. Without vigorous first-crosses, the most valuable classes of timbers can only be grown in limited quantity."

THE CAUSE OF VIGOR

Although many geneticists have speculated on the problem, no one has yet been able to offer a satisfactory explanation of the extraordinary vigor displayed by hybrids. Some of the Mendelian hypotheses put forward are plausible, but have so far remained unproven. The observed vigor, as Prof. Henry points out, "is distributed over the whole plant, and is as conspicuous in the roots as in the stem and leaves. What we actually observe is not only an acceleration of, but also an increase of cell-division in all parts of the plant. The cells divide very quickly, continue to divide, and thus build up a taller stem, a more extensive root-system, etc.

⁵ Bisset, Peter, "The James River Walnut." JOURNAL OF HEREDITY, V, 3, pp. 98-102, March, 1914.

NUTS OF THE SHELLBARK HICKORY

This is one of the commoner hickories of the central United States; its nuts, here shown natural size but without their husks, differ greatly from those of the pecan. The result of a cross between the two species is shown in Fig. 15, the following illustration. (Fig. 14.)

Apparently this alteration in the nature of the division of the cells is not associated with any visible change in their structure. Miss Marshall, who examined for me many sections of the growing points of hybrid poplars and their parent species, could find, as the result of three months' observations, no tangible differences in the size of the cells or nuclei, in the number of the chromosomes, etc.

"It is possible that the stimulus which causes growth (*i. e.*, cell-division) to commence and to continue is some soluble chemical compound or enzyme. The enzyme in the hybrid may be more complex and more effective than the enzymes in the species. Whether the injection of soluble matter obtained from a hybrid into the growing points of one of the parent species would stimulate the latter to increased cell-division, might be worth trying, if the experiment could be carried out.

"Whether the amount of vigor in hybrids is directly associated with the degree of relationship between the individuals which are crossed is a disputable point, but one of practical

interest in the selection of parents for crossing experiments. One of my most vigorous hybrids (*Populus generosa*) is derived from two parents so little related that they are placed in two distinct sections of the genus. A cross between two races of the common alder shows considerable vigor, though the parents are so closely allied that they can only be distinguished by the most trivial characters." But whatever the explanation of this vigor may be, no one who has worked with hybrids is likely to question its existence; and that fact is sufficient to make breeding justifiable.

PROPAGATION

"An important question is the propagation of these vigorous crosses, once they are created. The first-cross does not come true from seed, and it would be a great drawback if we were obliged to wait till the newly made trees bore flowers and fruit. The first-cross, in short, can only be multiplied by vegetative reproduction. This is easy when the trees are readily propagated by cuttings, as in the case of poplars and

willows, or by layers, like the Huntingdon and Belgian elms. We may resort to grafting low on stocks, which should be perhaps seedlings of one or other parent. This method will serve when cuttings and layers are not available. It is evident, that, when a valuable hybrid has been produced, it can be propagated and be put on the market, if necessary, without delay."

A few suggestions on the technique of cross-pollinating trees may be useful to those who want to try the artificial production of vigorous trees. Both

are receptive and a week after the cross-pollination has been made. If the tree with which one is working has perfect flowers and is to be used as the seed-bearing parent, the pollen-bearing organs must of course be removed at an early stage, with a needle-pointed forceps. This operation is a delicate one, particularly if it must be carried out at the top of a lofty tree, swaying in the wind. Sometimes it may not be necessary, if the flowers are protected by nature from self-pollination. In the case of the ash and elm, for example, the stigmas are receptive some days before the anthers shed their pollen. Under these circumstances, the pollen from another species may be applied to the stigma, and no attention paid to the anthers.

HANDLING TREE POLLEN

"Pollen spoils by keeping, but it often must be kept for some time till the stigma of the female parent is receptive. It is often obtained from distant countries where trees of the desired species, flowering early, can be found. It is best kept in a small glass tube either corked or plugged with cotton wool. Pollen is usually collected by cutting off the flowering twigs and placing them on white paper in a dry place for one or two days.

"Pollen is applied with a camel's hair brush, and a minute quantity is sufficient for each stigma. The stigmas are to be pollinated when receptive, indicated by the presence on them of a sugary solution or by their change to a brighter hue. Pollen grains may not be able to germinate on the stigma of another species, and yet be capable of fertilizing it, if germination could be induced. The transference of a drop of the substance secreted by the stigma of the pollen-bearing species to the stigma of the other parent might induce germination. The best time for pollination is in the warm part of the day, between 11 a. m. and 3 p. m. in early spring. Cold, wet days should be avoided."

It is not a very long time, in the history of the world, since the English gardener Fairchild produced the first

HYBRID NUT

Cross between pecan and shellbark hickory, borne by the tree shown in Fig. 12. The nut is natural size, and enclosed in its husk, one side of which has been removed. It is of small value, commercially. Photograph from the United States Department of Agriculture. (Fig. 15.)

male and female flowers should be protected with bags, in order to prevent the possibility of a mix-up in heredity through the presence of foreign pollen. The male flowers should be bagged a week before they shed their pollen, while the female flowers may be protected for a fortnight before the stigmas

artificial hybrid plant on record, in 1715, by fertilizing the stigma of a carnation with the pollen of a Sweet William. Since then, the process of artificial cross-pollination has transformed commercial horticulture and agriculture. There is good reason to believe that it will find an equally widespread application in forestry, and it is probable that Europe will undertake the work rather than the United States. The American continent still contains a large supply of virgin forest. Many years ago, however, the European forests passed the virgin stage and became the objects of thorough silvicultural management. They became an agricultural crop. Even in normal times the planted timber is recognized as entirely inadequate for the domestic requirements, but the present war has placed a responsibility upon the European forester greater than can possibly be appreciated. Timber reconnaissance, after the close of the war, will reveal an awful destruction of

forest growth. Never before in the history of the world has military activity been so destructive. The great battle wave, extending from Ostend to Belfort, and from Riga to Persia, flows to and fro, while artillery of unprecedented caliber, great jets of liquid fire, and clouds of deadly gases, reduce the forests to desolation. The strategic value of the forests, so often mentioned in official dispatches, but too plainly indicates approaching necessity for intensive reforestation projects, a work which will be so imperative as to render studies on accelerated reforestation of the greatest economic importance. The investigator, therefore, who can produce trees which will exceed the natural species in vigor, will be rendering the most valuable public service. If he can accelerate the reforestation of the battlefields of Belgium and France, he will be rendering a priceless contribution to the national welfare.

Wanted: A Plant Breeder

There is a possibility of an opening in teaching plant breeding in the Division of Agriculture at the Iowa State College. The candidate should have had some practical experience along plant industry

lines, preferably in horticulture. Further information may be had by addressing Professor S. A. Beach, head of the Department of Horticulture and Forestry, Ames, Iowa.

Eugenics and Military Preparedness

The relations of war to national eugenics have often been pointed out; the eugenic aspects of military preparedness are less often considered. Starting with the axiom that preparation for war should bear in mind the necessity of safeguarding national eugenics as far as possible, we arrive at the following conclusions:

1. A military establishment should be composed of men of as advanced an age as is compatible with military efficiency.

2. It should not be made up of celibates. Short enlistments might be valuable in favoring marriage.

3. Universal conscription would appear to be better than voluntary service, since the latter is highly selective.

4. Officer's families should be given an additional allowance in pay for each

child. This would aid in increasing the birth-rate, which appears to be very low among army and navy officers.

5. Means should be worked out to establish men, at the end of enlistment or the end of hostilities, as rapidly as possible economically, so that they may not be forced by economic pressure to refrain from marriage or parenthood.

6. "Preparedness," in the ordinary sense of the word, is highly desirable in order that the loss of men may be minimum, especially during early days of war when, if unready, a nation would probably lose heavily.

These appear to be some of the considerations, which should be regarded in advance of war, if the necessity for defense is to be made as little of a handicap, eugenically, to a nation as possible.